

1 **Hydrodynamics of Cascading Dam Failures: Flood Wave Propagation and Spillway Gate**
2 **Operations in the Edenville-Sanford Sequential Breach**

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5 **Abstract**

6 Aging high-hazard dams with limited spillway capacity face increasing risk from extreme
7 hydrologic events. The May 2020 Edenville-Sanford cascading dam failure in Michigan
8 exemplifies these vulnerabilities. In this study, we conducted a forensic and counterfactual
9 hydraulic analysis using a calibrated two-dimensional hydrodynamic model to reconstruct the
10 breach sequence and evaluate how alternative spillway gate operations influenced hydraulic
11 conditions related to breach initiation and downstream flood hazard. Our study examines four
12 spillway gate operation scenarios: (1) all gates closed, (2) gates open to 1.5 m, (3) gates open to
13 2.1 m, and (4) gates fully opened in advance of flood peak. The model was calibrated against the
14 satellite-derived flood extent and validated with high-water mark evidence. The model achieved
15 an F1 score of 0.66, demonstrating moderate spatial agreement in inundation extents. Although
16 some overprediction occurred in marginal floodplains, close agreement of inundation extent and
17 water surface elevation confirmed the model's reliability for scenarios analysis. Modeling results
18 show that the Edenville Dam breach could generate 4323 m³/s total peak flow, attenuated by 35%,
19 with peak arrival delayed approximately 3.5 hours before reaching Sanford Dam, located about 18
20 km downstream. Results inform that all gates closed and partially open scenarios produce water
21 surface elevation exceeding the breach-initiating thresholds at both dams, whereas full gates
22 opening could maintain safety margins and prevented breach entirely. The full opening scenario
23 can reduce downstream flood area by 31% and maximum depths from over 10 m to approximately
24 7 m compared to partial opening scenarios. Manning's roughness variations show less than 5%
25 change in breach peak flows, with breach timing and flood extents remaining consistent across all
26 scenarios. These findings demonstrate that partial gate openings were insufficient to prevent
27 failure, while full opening was critical for cascade prevention. Our results provide actionable
28 guidance for spillway gate operation protocols, emergency action planning, and dam safety
29 reviews at aging embankment dams with limited spillway capacity in sequential systems.

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36 Table S1. Computational mesh configurations and simulation performance.

Scenario	2D flow area (m)	Refinement region (m)	Simulation time (hh.mm.ss)
1	30×30	15×15	01.03.48
2	40×40	20×20	00.41.30
3	50×50	15×15	00.51.50
4	50×50	25×25	00.32.57
5	60×60	30×30	00.18.41
6	75×75	25×25	00.19.17
7	80×80	40×40	00.13.42

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38 Table S2. Performance

Performance metrics	Equation
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
Recall (Sensitivity)	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
F1 score	$2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$
F2 score	$(1 + \beta^2) \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{\beta^2 \times Precision + Recall}$
IoU (Jaccard Index)	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN}$

where TP = true positive (both datasets show flood), TN = true negative (both show no flood), FP = false positive (model predicts flood, observation shows no flood), and FN = false negative (observation show flood, model prediction no flood).

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40 Table S3. Calibrated values of manning's roughness coefficients for each land use class

ID	Land cover	Area (km ²)	(NRCS, 2016)	Calibrated	(Brunner, 2023)
0	NoData		0.025	0.025	0.025 – 0.035
1	Main channel		0.035	0.025	0.025 – 0.050
11	Open Water (2%)	17.0	0.035	0.030	0.025 – 0.050
21	Developed, Open Space (4.4%)	38.0	0.040	0.035	0.030 – 0.050
22	Developed, Low Intensity (5.1%)	44.5	0.100	0.066	0.060 – 0.120
23	Developed, Medium Intensity (1.1%)	9.2	0.080	0.080	0.080 – 0.160

24	Developed, High Intensity (0.1%)	1.1	0.150	0.120	0.120 – 0.200
31	Barren Land Rock-Sand-Clay (0.4%)	3.4	0.025	0.025	0.023 – 0.030
41	Deciduous Forest (4.8%)	41.7	0.160	0.100	0.100 – 0.200
42	Evergreen Forest (0.9%)	7.7	0.160	0.088	0.080 – 0.160
43	Mixed Forest (1.7%)	15.0	0.160	0.100	0.080 – 0.200
52	Shrub-Scrub (0.03%)	0.3	0.100	0.070	0.070 – 0.160
71	Grassland-Herbaceous (2.1%)	18.0	0.035	0.030	0.025 – 0.050
81	Pasture-Hay (0.6%)	5.0	0.030	0.030	0.025 – 0.050
82	Cultivated Crops (4.2%)	36.4	0.035	0.030	0.020 – 0.050
90	Woody Wetlands (15.4%)	133.7	0.120	0.063	0.045 – 0.150
95	Emergent Herbaceous Wetlands (0.7%)	5.9	0.070	0.055	0.050 – 0.085

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67 Figure S1. Land cover classification for the study area, dominated by the Woody Wetlands, followed
 68 by Developed Low Intensity and Deciduous Forest. Shrub/Scrub cover only 0.1% of the study
 69 area.

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71 Figure S2. Normalized breach progression curves for Edenville (formation time = 3.5 hours) and
 72 Sanford (formation time = 2.0 hours) dams. Breach fraction (0 = fully intact, 1 = complete breach)
 73 plotted against time fraction (0 = failure initiation, 1 = end of formation period). Edenville's
 74 exponential-decay shape reflects sudden embankment collapse in initial 30 seconds followed by
 75 gradual breach enlargement over subsequent hours, as captured in video recorded by Lynn
 76 Coleman (Coleman, 2020), while Sanford's Sine wave curve reflects steady-state erosion during
 77 overtopping. Edenville Dam's exponential-decay curve reflects the documented sudden
 78 embankment collapse (less than 30 seconds), captured in video, followed by gradual enlargement
 79 over 3.5 hours, producing peak discharge early in the event (50% breach achieved in approximately
 80 10.5 minutes). Sanford Dam's nearly linear progression reflects steady-state overtopping erosion
 81 with uniform widening throughout the 2-hour formation period (50% breach at 50% formation
 82 time). These mechanistically distinct patterns produce different peak discharge timing and
 83 downstream hydraulic signatures and are critical inputs for accurate hydrodynamic modeling of
 84 the cascade failure sequence.

Figure S3. Aerial view of Sanford Dam at 19:45 PM on 19 May 2020 during the flood event, prior to complete overtopping. Primary flow (blue arrow) shows the flow through main spillway, with secondary flow (red arrow) toward the fuse plug spillway. Flow over the spillway exhibits critical depth free-falling conditions, allowing accurate flow estimation using the 1D weir equation.

Figure S4. Aerial view of Sanford Dam at 20:30 on 19 May 2020 during the flood event, showing complete overtopping conditions. Flow occurs through the main spillway, over the fuse plug spillway, and across the dam embankment. Overtopping of the embankment increases tailwater elevation and crests submerged flow conditions, under which 2D flow modeling provides more accurate discharge estimations than 1D weir equation.

Figure S5. Samford Dam embankment with spillways and location at which cross-section taken to compute water surface elevation for Normal 2D weir equation and 1D weir equation (refer Figure S9).

Figure S6. Water surface elevation computed at Sanford Dam (ref Figure S8) with terrain profile. 1D weir equation produced high water surface elevation as compared to Normal 2D weir equation under submerged condition.

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87 Figure S7. Longitudinal profile of simulated water surface elevations under various mesh
 88 resolution scenarios. Five mesh configurations tested (Scenarios 1-5) show consistent results, with
 89 maximum deviations < 0.5 m in Scenarios 1 and 3.
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92 Figure S8. Mesh sensitivity and computational efficiency analysis for seven scenarios. Scenario-7
93 runs faster whereas Scenario-1 takes longer simulation.

Figure S9. Mesh sensitivity analysis showing water surface elevation at Sanford Dam for different cell size configurations. Left embankment sections of the fuse plug spillway (in red circle) remain above the simulated flood levels across all mesh configuration except for scenarios 6 and 7, whereas scenarios-1 and 3 water surface elevation is well below the embankment crest which is not true (refer Figure S5). Although, water surface profile simulated with Scenarios 2, 4 and 5 are aligned to each other and are below the embankment (in red circle), We selected the Scenario 5 for further analysis that takes relatively smaller simulation (approximately 18 minutes).

Figure S10. Post-flood satellite imagery of Sanford Dam collected from Maxar, showing flood extent, red circle indicates embankment remnants above flood water level.

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 105 Figure S11. Comparison of simulated flood maps with various sources with common scale, (A)
 106 flood extent (in red polygon, 9 km²) extracted from Google Earth and overlaid on the Maxar image
 107 on May 20 2020 (Image @ 2025 Maxar Technologies; Image @2025 CNES/Airbus), (B) Flood
 108 map extracted from the Landsat8 imagery (7.29 km²), (B) Sentinel-2 (5.73 km²), (C) Sentinel-1
 109 (5.99 km²) and (D) hydrodynamic simulation (14.61 km²). Among the various satellite derive flood
 110 maps Landsat8 produced the flood extent close to the Google Earth imagery, and it is taken for the
 111 model performance evaluation.

112 The satellite-derived flood map was generated using Landsat 8 Collection 2 Level 2 surface
 113 reflectance data within the Google Earth Engine (GEE) environment by applying a multi-temporal
 114 change detection workflow. Initial preprocessing included cloud and shadow masking via the
 115 QA_PIXEL bitmask, followed by the generation of pre-flood (April 1 to May 18, 2020) and post
 116 flood (May 19 to May 31, 2020) mosaics. MNDWI was calculated for both composites using the
 117 Green (Band 3) and SWIR1 (Band 6) bands to enhance the identification of open water features.
 118 Binary water masks were then established using a zero threshold (MNDWI >0.0), and the newly
 119 inundated areas were isolated by subtracting the pre-flood mask for the post-flood mask. To ensure
 120 the final extent was comparable to the HEC-RAS total wetted area, these newly flooded areas were
 121 merged with the baseline permanent water bodies to create a unified binary layer.

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124 Figure S12. Location of Michigan highway (M-30) Causeway bridge over the Wixom Lake with
 125 the flow direction of Tobacco River (A, Google Earth imagery). (B) Damaged section of the
 126 Causeway from May 20, 2020 flood event (“Flooding Devastates Mid-Michigan Region,” 2020)
 127 C) Simulated water surface elevation across the causeway showing the flooded road embankment
 128 north of the Edenville dam.

129 Figure S13. Location of M-30 bridge over the Tittabawassee River (A, Google Earth imagery). (B)
 130 Extensive structural damage to the bridge components with visible overtopping and pier scour
 131 damage, as documented by a Michigan Department of Transportation bridge engineer during post-
 132 flood inspections (D. Chalk, personal communication, May 20, 2020) (C) Simulated water surface
 133 elevation approximately 0.5 m to 1 m above the bridge deck, matching the observed overtopping
 134 that caused the bridge damage.

136 Figure S14. Location of W. Curtis Road bridge over the Tittabawassee River (A, Google Earth
 137 imagery). (B) Source causing extensive damage to the right embankment (“Flooding Devastates
 138 Mid-Michigan Region,” 2020). (C) simulated water surface elevation reaching approximately 200
 139 m across the river section, with water level roughly 2 m above the bridge deck. The model’s
 140 prediction of significant embankment overtopping at this location is consistent with the observed

141 erosion and damage patterns visible in field photographs. The relatively flat-water surface gradient
142 captured by the simulation reflects the broad floodplain inundation occurring downstream of the
143 spillway confluence point, where water from both the Tobacco River spillway and Tittabawassee
144 River spillway flow converge.

145 Figure S15. M-10 road bridge situated in the narrow valley over the Tittabawassee River just
146 upstream of the Sanford dam (A, Google Earth). (B) High water marks visible on the bridge piers
147 (Warren, Christopher/ USACE), providing field evidence of peak flood elevation. (C) simulated

148 water surface elevation reaching approximately 195 m above the river channel. Notably, simulated
149 water level corresponds closely to the field-observed high-water marks on the bridge pier. The
150 presence of these preserved high-water marks provides one of the most direct comparisons
151 available between model predictions and filed observations of peak flood elevation.

152 Figure S16. West Saginaw Road bridge over the Tittabawassee River approximately 680 m
 153 downstream of Sanford dam (A, Google Earth imagery). (B) picture taken from drone video taken
 154 on May 20, 2020 (Kreeeg Media, 2020), exhibiting the complete overtopped the bridge and road
 155 embankment (C) Photograph taken near the high flood level marker (approximately 3.6 m) on the
 156 left bank of the river near the bridge, captured by a U.S. Geological Survey hydrologic technician
 157 from the Upper Midwest Water Science Center during post-event field reconnaissance (J.
 158 Wilkinson, personal communication, May 20, 2020) (D) simulated water surface elevation,
 159 reaching approximately 193 m throughout the cross-section, with water level roughly 3 m above
 160 the bridge deck (in red circle). This location provides additional confirmation that the model
 161 accurately reproduces flood magnitudes and overtopping conditions at multiple locations,
 162 demonstrating consistency across the study domain.

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167 Figure S17. Longitudinal profile of simulated water surface elevations (WSE) for four spillway
 168 gate opening conditions: all gates close, 1.5 m, 2.1 m, and all gate fully open (3 m for Edenville
 169 and 3.1 m for Sanford). The horizontal dash lines denote breach initiating water surface elevation
 170 for Edenville and Sanford Dam. The results reveal that partial gate openings (0 m, 1.5 m, and 2.1
 171 m) produce nearly identical WSE profiles, with differences of less than 0.25 m, indicating that
 172 partial gate operations provide not significant flood attenuation benefits. In contrast, fully opening
 173 all gates substantially reduces WSE by approximately 1 to 5 m along the downstream reach. All
 174 gates open to 2.1 m represent the actual operating conditions during the flood event. All three
 175 scenarios (all gates close, all gates open to 1.5 m and all gates open to 2.1 m) resulted in WSE
 176 exceeding the breach-initiating threshold at both dams, whereas all gates fully opening provide
 177 some safety margin (less than 0.5 m for Edenville Dam and about 1 m for Sanford Dam) below
 178 the breach initiation thresholds.

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191 Figure S18. Water surface elevation for multiple gate operation conditions with reference spillway
 192 crest level (203.88 m), reservoir normal pool level (206.32 m), and dam crest (208.45 m) for
 193 Edenville Dam under no-breach condition. The red star represents the gate opening point. When
 194 all the gates remained fully closed, the reservoir responded directly to the inflow hydrograph,
 195 producing a rapid headwater rise, exceeding the dam crest elevation and eliminating freeboard and
 196 sustaining overtopping for several hours, a critical structural risk for the embankment. Under this
 197 condition, outflow transitioned to uncontrolled weir flow over both the spillway gates and the dam
 198 crest. Opening the gates to 1.5 m marginally reduced the peak stage but still resulted in overtopping
 199 for several hours. In this configuration, total downstream discharge was a combination of
 200 controlled gate outflow and uncontrolled weir flow. At a 2.1 m opening, anticipatory drawdown
 201 during the rising limb of the hydrograph, just below the dam crest thereby preventing overtopping
 202 and retaining limited flood storage capacity. This scenario achieved a balance between maintaining
 203 freeboard and moderating early releases. The full gate opening (3 m), produced the lowest peak
 204 stage at 206.58 m, preserving about 2 m of freeboard. However, this configuration generated an
 205 earlier and larger outflow pulse, reducing the reservoir's ability to attenuate downstream
 206 hydrograph. While both 2.1 m and 3.0 m opening conveyed flow entirely through the gated
 207 spillways, the latter's reduced attenuation potential could exacerbate downstream peak stage if
 208 coinciding with other flood wave arrivals.

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211 Figure S19. Kernel density estimation (KDE) of simulated flood depths under four spillway gate
 212 operation scenarios: fully closed (0 m), partially open (1.5 m and 2.1 m), and fully open at both
 213 Edenville and Sanford Dam. The fully open gate scenario produced a unimodal flood depth
 214 distribution with a dominant peak at approximately 4.5 m, while the closed and partially open gate
 215 scenarios exhibited bimodal distributions with primary peaks at 4.5 m to 5 m and secondary peaks
 216 around 6.5 m to 7.5 m. This indicates that restricted gate operations not only increase spatial
 217 heterogeneity in flood depths but also generate localized areas of substantially deeper inundation.
 218 Notably, the similar distributions among the restricted gate openings indicate that partial gate
 219 openings offer little flood reduction benefit, emphasizing the need for full gate operation during
 220 extreme events.

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226 Figure S20. Sensitivity of Manning's roughness to breach peak flow (A) and breach hydrograph
 227 (B) for Edenville Dam. No significant change in breach peak flow, with Overall change in
 228 roughness ($\pm 20\%$) is relatively sensitive to peak flow. Importantly, time to peak is same under all
 229 scenarios. (C) Sensitivity of Manning's roughness to water surface elevation at Sanford Dam (C)
 230 and (D). Overall change in Manning's roughness is sensitive to the water surface elevation as

231 compared to individual change in roughness coefficients for different land covers. (E) Sensitivity
 232 of Manning's roughness to mean of longitudinal water surface elevation. (F) longitudinal water
 233 surface elevation under varying Manning's roughness coefficient. Base case is the calibrated model
 234 with 2.1 m gate opening.

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 236 Figure S21. Kernel density estimation, showing flood depth density distribution under the variation
 237 in Manning's roughness coefficient ($\pm 20\%$). The flood depth distribution remained relatively
 238 stable across all Manning's n sensitivity scenarios, with the overall and channel roughness
 239 parameters showing the greatest influence on depth predictions. Variation in Manning's n resulted
 240 in only minor shifts in the flood depth distribution, indicating that the model predictions are robust
 241 to reasonable uncertainties in roughness parameterization.

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 243 **References**

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